

Selecting High-Yielding Apricot Varieties Suitable for the Soil and Climatic Conditions of Fergana Region

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Abstract: *The article discusses the results of research aimed at identifying apricot varieties with the highest yield and best fruit quality among local and introduced varieties, as well as those resistant to the main diseases of apricot. According to the research findings, a group of varieties suitable for adaptive horticulture requirements has been identified. For newly established and reconstructed orchards, the apricot varieties 'Oq Nuqul', 'Bogishamol', 'Oq qandak', and 'Yubiley Navoi' are recommended for their high yield potential.*

Keywords: *adaptive, apricot, clasterosporium, yield, quality, sugar content, local, introduction.*

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Research methodology

Researches on the study of local and introduced varieties of apricot in a collection garden established on a low-fertility, stony-gravel land of Fergana region, located at an altitude of 450 meters above sea level. is conducted on the basis of accepted methodology [1;2;3;4].

Research Results and Their Analysis:

At the Fergana Scientific Experimental Station of the Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture, and Winemaking named after Academician M. Mirzayev, collection orchards of several apricot varieties have been preserved among stone fruits, including varieties brought from different geographic regions.

Despite some achievements in this field, stone fruit varieties require constant updates. This is due to the ongoing climate changes on Earth, which necessitate the continuous enrichment of existing collection orchards with varieties resistant to climate and weather fluctuations.

Due to damage from the recurrent spring frost in 2022, the following varieties among the storage-resistant apricots exhibited poor performance: Shalakh, Venger Luchshiy, and Asaka alola. Among the varieties suitable for pickling, Kursodik and Subkhani showed low yields. However, a number of varieties demonstrated resilience to the variable spring climate conditions. Specifically, the apricot yields per hectare were 68.6–81.3 quintals for Oq Nuqul and Bogishamol, and 63.3–74 quintals for Oq Qandak and Yubiley Navoi (see Table 1).

Table 1. Yield of various apricot varieties

№	Variety Name	Yield, hundredweight/ha			Additional Yield, hundredweight/ha		
		2022	2023	average	2022	2023	average
Canning Varieties							
1	Shalakh (control)	-	78,9	39,4	-	-	-
2	Oq Nuqul	68,6	59,3	63,9	68,6	-19,6	24,5
3	Venger. Luchsh.	-	75,9	37,9	-	-1,5	-0,75
4	Bogishamol	81,3	81,2	81,2	81,3	2,3	41,8
5	Asaka lola	-	58,6	29,3	-	-20,3	-10,1
Drying Varieties							
1	Kursodik (control)	-	62,1	31	-	-	-
2	Oq Qandak	65,3	63,7	64,5	65,3	1,6	33,5
3	Subkhani	-	109	54,5	-	46,9	23,5
4	Yu.Navoi	74	80,1	77	74	18	46
2022-2023 Average: NSR₀₅ = 7.9 hundredweight /ha, NSR₀₅ = 11.1%							

Note: Due to spring frost in 2022, some varieties did not bear fruit.

In the favorable year of 2023 for apricots, the Shalakh variety, taken as the standard for canning varieties, yielded 78.9 centners per hectare. Only the Bogishamol variety surpassed this, producing 81.2 centners per hectare, which was 2.3 centners more than the standard. In contrast, the Vengerskaya Luchshaya, Oq Nuqul, and Asaka Lola varieties yielded 1.5, 19-20 centners less than the control variety, respectively.

An analysis of the yield for drying varieties indicates that the highest yield was recorded in the Subkhani variety. In particular, the Subkhani variety yielded 109 centners per hectare, producing an additional 46.9 centners compared to the Kursodik variety, which was taken as the standard.

In the Yubiley Navoi variety, the yield reached 80.1 centners per hectare, producing an additional 18 centners. In the Oq Qandak variety, the apricot yield was at the same level as the standard Kursodik variety, with a yield of 63.7 centners per hectare and an additional yield of 1.6 centners.

For the years 2022-2023, which had varying weather conditions, positive results were observed in the canning varieties Oq Nuqul and Bogishamol, with an additional yield of 24.5-41.8 centners on average compared to the control variety.

Among the drying varieties, stable positive results were recorded in the Oq Qandak and Yubiley Navoi varieties, with an additional yield of 33.5-46 centners compared to the standard Kursodik variety.

In 2023, a year with favorable weather for apricots, the analysis showed that drying apricot varieties outperformed canning varieties in terms of overall fruit quality. The average fruit weight in the canning variety Shalakh reached 45 grams, while the largest fruit among the drying varieties was recorded in Yubiley Navoi, with a weight of 34 grams (Table 2).

Although the canning varieties showed superiority in terms of fruit size, the drying varieties achieved better results in all other quality indicators. Specifically, the appearance of the fruit in canning varieties was rated at 3.0-4.0 points, while the drying varieties were rated higher, at 4.0-4.4

points. The highest ratings were given to Oq Nuqul (4 points) among the canning varieties and Yubiley Navoiy (4.4 points) among the drying varieties.

In terms of taste, the highest scores were awarded to the Shalakh (4.0 points) and Oq Qandak (4.6 points) varieties.

The measurement of total sugar content in the fruit showed that Shalakh (14.2%) led among the canning varieties, while Oq Qandak (31.5%) was the best among the drying varieties. Regarding overall fruit quality, the highest results were recorded for Shalakh(3.7 points) among the canning varieties and Oq Qandak (4.3 points) among the drying varieties. The variable spring weather conditions in some regions of our country create unfavorable conditions for the vital processes of stone fruit trees. However, the soil and climatic conditions in the Fergana region

Table 2. Fruit quality of various apricot varieties

№	Variety name	Single Fruit Weight, grams		Appearance (points)		Taste (points)		Sugar Content (%)		Overall Quality (points)	
		2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023
Canning Varieties											
1	Shalakh (control)	-	45	-	3,4	-	4	-	14,2	-	3,7
2	Oq Nuqul	31	31	4	4	3,8	3	11,3	10,3	4	3,5
3	Venger. Luchsh.	-	32	-	3,5	-	3,5	-	14,1	-	3,5
4	Bogishamol	34	34	3,5	3	3	3,5	10,5	10,5	3,5	3,2
5	Asaka lola	-	35	-	3,6	-	3,8	-	12	-	3,3
Drying Varieties											
1	Kursodik (control)	-	29	-	4,2	-	4,5	-	27,4	-	4,2
2	Oq Qandak	27	27	4	4	4,8	4,6	15,8	31,5	4,2	4,3
3	Subkhani	-	33,2	-	4	-	4,5	-	21,8	-	4,2
4	Yu.Navoi	39	34	3,5	4,4	4	4,1	13	21,5	4,5	4

Note: In 2022, some varieties did not bear fruit due to spring frost.

are considered favorable for stone fruits, especially apricots.

Despite this, climatic changes are causing significant damage to fruit orchards due to various fungal diseases.

When establishing new orchards, it is important to prioritize varieties with valuable economic traits while considering their resistance to pathogens, as well as understanding the characteristics of the development of certain disease-causing agents [5].

One such disease that affects the commercial quality of apricot fruit is Clasterosporium.

It is known that the pathogen of shot hole disease is "Clasterosporium carpophilum" (Aderh.), while infectious dieback is caused by fungi "Cytospora cincta" Sacc., "C. leucostoma" Fr., and the bacterium "Pseudomonas syringae" van Hall (6; 7; 8; 9).

Clasterosporium disease has a severe impact on apricot yield and fruit quality. The disease damages the apricot leaves and fruit, leading to a reduction in the plant's photosynthesis process and a decrease in its immunity to other fungal diseases. Research at the Fergana Scientific and Experimental Station, particularly on new apricot varieties created there and those introduced from other climatic regions, allows for the identification of varieties with disease resistance and adaptability for production and selection purposes.

The Clasterosporium disease primarily overwinters in the form of mycelium and conidia in tree bark, buds, and gum. During the growing season, it causes holes in leaves and, more severely, pitted, necrotic lesions on the fruit. Research has shown that all apricot varieties studied exhibit varying degrees of susceptibility to Clasterosporium (Table 3).

Among the apricot varieties, no completely resistant or highly tolerant varieties were found. However, early varieties and canning varieties showed lower levels of infection compared to drying varieties, which were more frequently affected. The level of infection and tolerance was assessed using a 9-point scale according to international standards [10]. For instance, if the disease affected 11-25% of the plant or leaf area, it was rated as a 3 on the scale, with a tolerance level of 5.

Among the early ripening, canning-suitable varieties, 'Shalakh,' 'Oq nuqul,' 'Bog'ishamol,' and 'Vengerskiy luchshiy' were evaluated as weakly affected varieties, with damage from Clasterosporium on leaves and fruits being less than 10%. These varieties were found to have high resistance to the Clasterosporium disease, with a rating of 7 points.

Table 3. Degree of Clasterosporium Disease Infection in Apricot Varieties

№	Variety name	Infection (%)				Tolerance Level (points)	
		Leaves		Fruit		2022	2023
		2022	2023	2022	2023		
Canning Varieties							
1	Shalakh (control)	9	6	-	5	7	7
2	Oq Nuqul	7	5	5	4	7	7
3	Venger. Luchsh.	9	6	-	5	7	7
4	Bogishamol	6	5	5	4	7	7
5	Asaka lola	6	4	-	4	7	7
Drying Varieties							
1	Kursodik (control)	16	15	-	14	5	5
2	Oq Qandak	15	14	14	12	5	5
3	Subkhani	15	14	-	12	5	5
4	Yu.Navoi	14	13	12	11	5	5

Note: In 2022, some varieties did not produce fruit due to spring frost.

The relatively low infection levels in these varieties can also be explained by their shorter vegetation period and early ripening. Research has shown that drying varieties, in the dry spring conditions of 2023, experienced less infection compared to 2022 but still had lower resistance compared to canning varieties.

Specifically:

- Kursodik showed 15% infection in leaves and 14% in fruit.
- Oq Qandak had 14% infection in leaves and 12% in fruit.
- Subkhani experienced 14% infection in leaves and 12% in fruit.

These varieties displayed weak infection levels and average tolerance (5 points). This indicates that no apricot varieties are completely resistant to Clasterosporium. Therefore, the presence of this disease in all apricot orchards necessitates ongoing selection efforts for resistant varieties. It is crucial to continue selecting adaptive varieties from both local and introduced ones for their resistance to Clasterosporium and other fungal diseases.

Therefore, for establishing new orchards in areas with low soil fertility, we recommend the following apricot varieties based on their yield, fruit quality, and resistance to *Clasterosporium* disease:

- Canning Varieties: Oq Nuqul and Bogishamol
- Drying Varieties: Oq Qandak and Yubiley Navoiy

These varieties are noted for their higher productivity, better fruit quality, and greater resistance to the *Clasterosporium* disease, making them suitable choices for challenging conditions.

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